

Fufu Food Target Product Profile Workplan, at NRCRI-Nigeria

Kampala, Uganda, October 2025

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This report has been written in the framework of the RTBfoodomics project (under CIRAD coordination), as a continuation of work initiated under the RTBfoods and RTB Breeding projects.

To be cited as:

Ugo CHIJOKE, Simon Peter ABAH (2025). *Fufu Food Target Product Profile Workplan*, at NRCRI-Nigeria. Umudike, Nigeria: RTBfoodomics, Institute Roadmap, 15 p. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17610490>

Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the RTBfoodomics, through a grant from the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF) to the French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development (CIRAD), Montpellier, France, incorporated in the grant agreement INV-054662_2024 between CIRAD and BMGF.

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ABSTRACT

The RTBfoodomics project officially started with a kickoff and planning meeting organized at CIAT (Cali, Colombia) in March 2025. This gathering brought together the partners of the project to align on project activities and responsibilities. Defining a standard sampling protocol was of particular importance.

Following the meeting, NRCRI produced a detailed workplan outlining the genotypes to be harvested and the samples to be produced and analyzed. The sampling protocol was discussed at length to ensure enough replications of each genotype were included in the workplans (at planting, harvesting and sample preparation).

The NRCRI phenotyping and sampling strategy will focus on 60 cassava genotypes targeting core traits essential for high-quality fufu production, i.e. retting ability, textural properties, and colour. Genotypes from UYT, PYT, Genetic Gain populations, and landraces are planted under controlled field designs to ensure robust trait expression and minimize environmental variability. Each genotype will be harvested at 12 months after planting, with six biological replicates selected for metabolomic analysis. Roots will undergo standardized retting in genotype-specific vats, with environmental parameters (pH, turbidity, temperature) monitored to assess processing efficiency. Cooked fufu samples will be evaluated using harmonized SOPs for instrumental texture analysis and sensory profiling. Sensory traits including moldability, stickiness, and smoothness will be scored by trained panels comprising processors, consumers, and scientists. Colour will be measured at three processing stages using chromameter readings and visual assessments. Samples from fresh root, retted mash, and cooked fufu will be freeze-dried and shipped to RHUL for metabolomic profiling. This integrated design ensures reliable data capture across traits and supports the selection of 15 representative genotypes for deeper biochemical analysis. The results will inform breeding strategies and enable the development of molecular markers linked to consumer-preferred fufu quality traits.

Key Words: Fufu, Phenotyping, Retting Ability, Cassava, Instrumental Texture Analysis, Sensory Evaluation, Colour, Metabolomic, Alpha Lattice Design

1 PHENOTYPING SAMPLES

1.1 Phenotyping Using Harmonized SOPs: Core Traits for Fufu Product Profile

Retting ability, textural properties and colour, have been defined as the core traits for *Fufu* Food Target Product Profile. These attributes are critical for evaluating the processing quality, end-user preferences and genotype selection potential of cassava varieties intended for Fufu production. All assessments will follow harmonized phenotyping standard operating procedures (SOPs) validated and approved under the RTBfoods project hence ensuring consistency across measurements and environments (Appendices 1-7).

A total of **sixty cassava genotypes** from diverse origins have been selected for this study. Within this set, at least **fifteen genotypes** will be identified to represent the full spectrum of phenotypic trait expression (high/good, intermediate, and low/poor) for each target quality attribute. This strategic sampling ensures sufficient phenotypic variation for robust statistical analyses, trait correlation studies, and downstream applications in breeding and product development.

1.2 Phenotyping for Retting Ability:

Retting ability, an essential determinant of root softening and processing efficiency, will be phenotyped using a combination of instrumental and expert-based approaches. pH and turbidity temperature will be measured at defined intervals during the retting process using calibrated meters to monitor diversity in retting ability of different cassava genotypes. In parallel, fufu champion processors will be used to monitor physical preference/ degree of root softening and ease of defibering or sieving fermented roots using a standardized five-point scale. The number of hours or days required to achieve optimal retting will also be recorded alongside chaff loss and fufu yield. All measurements will be guided by RTBfoods Harmonised SOPs developed for fufu processing and retting ability to ensure repeatability and reproducibility across trials and seasons (Appendices 1 and 2)

1.3 Phenotyping for Instrumental Texture Attributes:

Fufu, will be assessed instrumentally using Penetration and Extrusion tests with texture analyzer to measure parameters such as hardness, cohesiveness, adhesiveness and stretchability. These measurements will follow harmonized SOP protocols for sample preparation and Fufu instrumental texture analysis. The outcomes will quantify and classify genotypes based on their fufu textural properties (Appendices 3 and 4).

1.4 Phenotyping for Sensory Properties:

Visual or Sensory approach will be employed to determine textural properties of fufu using the Quantitative Descriptive Sensory approach by 10-12 trained panelists. This study will capture traits such as moldability, stickiness and smoothness of Fufu. Trained panelists will assess these traits using the validated SOPs for determining sensory attributes of fufu under the RTBfoods project (Appendices 3 to 7).

1.5 Phenotyping for Colour:

Colour will be assessed at three critical stages of Fufu processing—namely, the fresh cassava root, the intermediate retted mash, and the final cooked Fufu—instrumentally (using a chromameter) as well as visually by trained (for the cooked product) and champion processors (for fresh and intermediate products). The chromameter will record L* (lightness), a* (red-green), and b* (yellow-blue) values, enabling the objective evaluation of visual appeal and colour retention across processing stages. These values will help differentiate genotypes based on the colour component (Appendices 5, 6 and 7).

1.6 Environmental/Physiological Conditions during the Phenotyping Process

Phenotyping of the core traits for Fufu—specifically, retting ability, colour and textural properties—must be conducted using cassava samples that display distinct variation across genotypes. This variation should include high, intermediate, and low expression levels for each trait. The accuracy and comparability of phenotypic data depend significantly on the environmental, physiological, and post-harvest conditions under which the phenotyping is executed.

Cassava roots will be harvested at a consistent physiological stage, specifically at 12 months after planting (MAP), corresponding to a well-recognized maturity period for most genotypes. This maturity stage ensures adequate root bulking, optimal starch accumulation, and alignment with end-user expectations for Fufu quality. All harvested roots will be processed within 24 hours to prevent the onset of post-harvest physiological deterioration (PPD), which can affect colour stability, retting dynamics, and texture properties.

After harvesting, cassava roots will be immediately peeled and washed. A retting process will follow, involving the submersion roots in water under ambient environmental conditions. To ensure comparability, the retting environmental conditions (typically between 25°C to 35°C) will be monitored, and fermentation indicators such as pH, temperature, turbidity, loss of firmness, chaff loss and fufu yield will be recorded at defined intervals. These parameters will support the assessment of retting ability by capturing the factor(s) responsible for textural softening, and sensory properties of fufu. Roots will then be further processed into Fufu according to SOP-defined protocol.

2 DEFINITION OF GENOTYPES TO SCREEN

A central focus during the planning and preparatory meetings for this Fufu Food Target Product Profile (FTPP) was to define an appropriate set of cassava genotypes that would ensure sufficient contrast in the core traits during harvesting and processing. These traits include retting ability, textural properties and colour—all essential for characterizing suitability for Fufu production.

Given the complexity of Fufu quality phenotyping and its dependence on genotypic diversity, environmental interaction, and fermentation behavior, the strategy for genotype selection was designed to maximize phenotypic contrasts rather than relying on a pre-fixed panel. For this purpose, a broad set of 60 cassava genotypes derived from a biparental population was selected for an initial screening. These genotypes are currently grown (**Table 1**) under field conditions in an alpha lattice design, which supports robust statistical analysis of trait performance.

The selected population encompasses lines that have previously shown variability in processing behavior, starch content, root yield, and pasting profiles, making them ideal candidates for screening against the core Fufu traits. The intention is to evaluate all 60 genotypes using the harmonized phenotyping SOPs. From this a subset of genotypes, (minimum of fifteen will be identified based on their distinct expression of the core traits—spanning high, intermediate, and low performance classes.

Only genotypes that display the desirable range of variability will be advanced to the next phase, which includes sample preparation and metabolomic profiling. Freeze-dried samples will be prepared from three processing stages—fresh root, intermediate retted mash, and final cooked Fufu—and shipped to RHUL for metabolomic analysis. This targeted approach allows for optimization of analytical resources while ensuring that the selected genotypes provide a robust biochemical and phenotypic foundation for understanding Fufu quality.

By combining broad initial screening with strategic sample curation, this genotype selection approach will provide a comprehensive and efficient platform for identifying the biochemical underpinnings of Fufu quality traits and supporting trait-informed breeding decisions.

2.1 Brief Description of the Origin of the Genotypes to Test

The genotypes selected for this study on Fufu product profile comprise 60 cassava materials representing diverse genetic backgrounds from multiple breeding pipelines within NRCRI Breeding lines (Table 1). These genotypes were purposefully chosen to reflect both genetic and phenotypic variability relevant to Fufu processing quality traits such as retting ability, colour and textural properties.

A total of 34 genotypes were drawn from a biparental population (NR20C3) representing advanced breeding lines currently under evaluation in the Uniform Yield Trials (UYT), specifically UYT Set 1 and UYT Set 2 (some having historical data on retting ability and textural properties). These genotypes are currently established in multi-location fields testing for agronomic performance, root dry matter, evaluation of physicochemical properties, processing attributes and retting ability. **Considering the heterozygosity of progenitors in cassava**, the biparental nature of this group ensures structured genetic segregation and a high likelihood of quantitative trait expression relevant for both metabolic diversity and processing attributes.

In addition to these **34 genotypes** derived from the biparental populations, **three landraces** (*Nwaibibi*, *Wonono*, and *Nwaocha*) **clones** have also been included to represent contrasting end-user preferences and processing characteristics. This composite panel increases the relevance of the study to real-world food system needs while capturing a wide range of genetic and phenotypic diversity.

Six genotypes (NR23SP02P001, NR23SP03P002, NR23SP04P003, NR23SP05P004, NR23SP06P005, and NR23SP06P006) were selected from the Preliminary Yield Trials (PYT), which represent early-generation breeding materials exhibiting promising quality-related traits. These PYT lines were chosen based on preliminary observations on root morphology, dry matter content, and fermentation response under local processing conditions (Table 1).

Table 1: Summary of the germplasm (Planted in Umudike, Nigeria) to screen.

SN	Genotype	Phenotypic score				Planting Date	Harvesting Date	Number of	
		RAb	Coh	Mol	Col			Reps	Plants
1	NR20C3F2P0020	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
2	NR20C3F2P0017					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
3	NR20C3F3P0024	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
4	NR20C3F8P0014	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
5	NR20C3F24P0003	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
6	NR20C3F3P0031	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
7	NR20C3F22P0005	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
8	NR20C3F19P0001	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
9	NR20C3F2P0012	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
10	NR20C3F9P0006	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
11	NR20C3F2P0033	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
12	NR20C3F16P0015	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
13	NR20C3F4P0002	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
14	NR20C3F4P0040	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
15	NR20C3F4P0067	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
16	NR20C3F3P0019	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
17	NR20C3F17P0015	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
18	NR20C3F8P0001					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
19	NR20C3F2P0020					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
20	NR20C3F16P0048					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
21	NR20C3F36P0002	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
22	NR20C3F36P0004					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
23	NR20C3F38P0003					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
24	NR20C3F3P0026					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
25	NR20C3F4P0078					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
26	NR20C3F5P0008	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
27	NR20C3F7P0008					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
28	NR20C3F7P0013					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
29	NR20C3F8P0007					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
30	NR20C3F19P0006					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
31	NR20C3F24P0001	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
32	NR20C3F3P0010					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
33	NR20C3F4P0005					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
34	NR20C3F4P0023					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
35	Nwaibibi					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
36	NR17C2aF16P004					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
37	Wonono					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
38	Headmaster					Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
39	TMS980505	x	x	x	x	Oct, 2024	Sep, 2025	3	36
40	CR41-10					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
41	IBA30572					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
42	IBA980581					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
43	No Hunger	x	x	x	x	Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
44	Poundable					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
45	TMS13F1160P0004					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
46	UMUCASS36	x	x	x	x	Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
47	UMUCASS38					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
48	IBA920057					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
49	OBASANJO2					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
50	Hope					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	3	24
51	BABA70	x	x	x	x	Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	2	10
52	TME419					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	2	10
53	NR87184	x	x	x	x	Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	2	10

Table 1 cont.

SN	Genotype	Phenotypic score				Planting	Harvesting	Number of	
		RAb	Coh	Mol	Col			Date	Reps
54	NR20SP02P001					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	2	10
55	NR20SP03P002					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	2	10
56	NR20SP04P003					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	2	10
57	NR20SP05P004					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	2	10
58	NR20SP06P005					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	2	10
59	NR20SP06P006					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	2	10
60	Nwaocha					Jun,2024	Apr, 2025	2	10

RAb: retting ability; **Coh:** Cohesiveness; **Mol:** Moldability; **Col:** Colour

The remaining 17 genotypes (NR17C2aF16P00, Headmaster, TMS980505, CR41-10, IBA30572, IBA980581, No Hunger, Poundable, TMS13F1160P0004, UMUCASS36, UMUCASS38, IBA920057, OBASANJO2, Hope, BABA70, TME419, and NR87184) comprising a diverse collection of elite and pre-elite lines derived from international and regional crossing programs were sourced from the Genetic Gain (GG) population at NRCRI, Umudike. This group includes high-performing lines selected for yield stability, improved starch functionality, and tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses. Their integration into the panel will also support a wide metabolic and genotypic representation, particularly in relation to traits with known environmental sensitivity, such as retting ability and textural properties of fufu.

Although information on the retting ability and textural attributes of most of the materials are yet to be formally published, internal food quality, breeding and agronomic evaluations have shown stable performance across seasons for certain traits. All phenotypic data will be collected following the harmonized SOPs to minimize measurement error and ensure reproducibility. These efforts are expected to strengthen downstream metabolomic analysis by providing a well-structured, trait-diverse genotype panel with controlled sampling protocols and reliable and contrasting phenotype references. **Figure 1** shows the description of 49 genotypes at AYT already phenotyped for their retting ability clustered into three distinct retting quality (good, moderate and poor). **It is from this population that the 34 genotypes (currently in UYT) were selected from.**

2.2 Alternative Back-up Germplasm or Sources of Sampling

Given this extensive diversity, there is high confidence that the 60 selected materials will provide sufficient discrimination across the core traits to allow for the subsequent identification of the 15 genotypes (5 good, 5 intermediate and 5 poor) that is required to conduct the metabolomic profiling in the project.

As such, there is foreseen alternative or back-up germplasm for this study. The current set of 60 genotypes is more than adequate to generate the desired phenotypic variability, enabling a focused selection of the 15 most representative lines for the metabolomic analysis. These selected genotypes will span the full spectrum of trait expression—ranging from high/good to low/poor performance for each core trait—ensuring the quality and robustness of the metabolomic data generated from these samples.

Figure 1: Description of the genotypes into three clusters based on their retting ability.

In the unlikely event that some genotypes fail to produce adequate root material for analysis, or if there is an unexpected loss of sample quality, additional genotypes from the same breeding populations (UYT, PYT, or Genetic Gain) could be substituted. However, this contingency is considered highly unlikely given the ample sample sizes available. Furthermore, the careful selection process has already ensured that the 60 materials cover a broad range of genotypic and phenotypic diversity, minimizing the need for supplementary germplasm.

Thus, with more than enough genetically and phenotypically diverse materials to sample from, the planned 15-subset for metabolomic analysis will be fully supported by the initial screening of the 60 materials, without requiring alternative sources of germplasm.

3 SAMPLING STRATEGY AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

3.1 Experimental design

The process of harvesting, sampling, phenotyping, and preparing samples for the metabolomic analysis has been carefully planned to ensure the reliable capture of data and to meet the requirements of the Fufu Food Target Product Profile (FTPP). A critical aspect of this study is the need to generate robust data across multiple traits (physicochemical Texture, sensory, colour evaluation and retting ability) from a diverse range of genotypes, all of which are part of the broader cassava breeding program. Also relevant is the production of samples that properly represent/maintain the biochemical properties of the tissues being analyzed.

The 60 selected genotypes, representing a combination of materials from the UYT, PYT, Genetic Gain populations and selected landraces, are already planted in the field, with the experimental designs in place as described below.

For the UYT (Uniform Yield Trials) population, each genotype is planted in plots measuring 6 x 6 meters (totaling 36 stands) and replicated three times (Table 1). This plot size and replication are designed to ensure that the genotypes are grown under standardized conditions and to minimize the impact of environmental variability, allowing for robust data collection on the key traits of interest.

For the Genetic Gain population, each genotype is planted in plots measuring 4 x 5 meters (totaling 24 stands), with sufficient replication to ensure reliable results (Table 1). This design will allow for comprehensive analysis of traits such as retting ability and paste cohesiveness, which can be more sensitive to environmental factors.

For the PYT (Preliminary Yield Trials), which include early-generation breeding materials with potentially greater G×E (genotype-by-environment) interactions, each genotype is planted in plots measuring 2 x 5 meters (totaling 10 stands, Table 1). This smaller plot size allows for a more efficient experimental design, considering the larger number of genotypes involved in the trial. The use of an Alpha Lattice Design will also help to account for environmental variability and ensure accurate genotype comparisons.

The sampling process will involve the following steps (**Figure 2**):

1. **Harvesting:** All 60 genotypes will be harvested at the standardized age of 12 months after planting (MAP) to ensure consistency in root maturity and starch accumulation.
2. **Sampling of Roots:** **Three roots from six stands from each genotype will be carefully selected to ensure representative sampling of the genotypic variability. These six stands will represent the six biological replications required for metabolomic analysis. After harvest, the roots will be peeled and washed immediately to avoid any post-harvest deterioration that may affect sample quality. Only healthy roots will be used for processing and phenotyping.**
3. **Retting:** The freshly harvested roots will be soaked in water in individual fermenting vats (all roots from the same genotype in a single vat) and monitored under controlled conditions as retting progresses lasting up to 72 hours. The retting environment will be monitored for temperature, pH, and other relevant factors to ensure consistency (e.g., foaming ability and water clarity should be measured at 24 h, while penetrometer, hardness, turbidity, pH, and total titratable acidity data are best collected after 36 h).
4. **Cooking and Phenotyping:** Cooked Fufu samples will be prepared according to the RTBfoods project validated and approved standard operating protocols (SOPs). The core traits (fufu texture, retting ability, processing parameters, colour) will be assessed using both sensory evaluation and instrumental techniques, as outlined in the Fufu profile.
5. **Freeze-Drying and Sample Shipment:** The six samples from each genotype, including fresh root, intermediate retted mash, and final cooked paste, will be freeze-dried and carefully packaged for shipment to the RHUL for metabolomic analysis (Figure 2).

The study is designed with at least six biological replications per genotype to ensure sufficient statistical power for identifying genotype performance across all traits. This replication strategy, coupled with the carefully controlled experimental designs, will allow for robust data generation and enable accurate assessments of trait variability, which is essential for selecting the 15 genotypes that will undergo further metabolomic profiling.

Figure 2: Diagram of the entire sampling and processing strategy.

3.2 Sensory Evaluation of Fufu Samples

The sensory panel will be conducted on the 60 **selected genotypes** based on preliminary screening results (e.g., physicochemical and processing characteristics such as dry matter content, retting efficiency, cohesiveness, and moldability). **Fifteen clones** will be chosen to represent the phenotypic diversity across the 60-genotype biparental population.

Sensory evaluation will be carried out by a trained panel comprising local Fufu processors, consumers, and food scientists at NRCRI and its surrounding area. Evaluated traits will include:

- **Appearance (color, smoothness)**
- **Texture (Hardness/ softness, moldability, cohesiveness and stickiness)**
- **Champion Processing evaluation (scale of 1-5 will be used to evaluate loss of firmness or hardness root, ease of sieving of roots while fufu yield and chaff loss will calculate d on percentage basis based initial weight used for processing)**

Each attribute will be scored on a 1- 10-point descriptive scale. The sensory evaluation results will complement metabolomic data to define consumer-relevant product profiles and enable the development of molecular markers for sensory-associated traits in cassava breeding.

4 CHRONOGRAM OF ACTIVITIES

The following tentative chronogram outlines the main project milestones, from field phenotyping to laboratory-based sensory and metabolomic analyses. Activities include planting, harvesting, wet lab phenotyping, sensory panel testing, and shipment of samples to partner laboratories (freeze-dried samples to RHUL for).

Table 2: Tentative Chronogram of Activities.

Field	Phenotyping (wet lab)	Sensory Panel	Sample Shipment
June	X (the PYT materials)	X (the PYT materials)	
July	X (the Genetic Gain materials)	X (the Genetic Gain materials)	
August			
September	X (the UYT materials)	X(the UYT materials)	
October	X(the UYT materials)	X(the UYT materials)	
November			X (15 selection for high, intermediate and poor) retting materials
December			X (15 selection for high, intermediate and poor) retting materials

APPENDICE

Appendix 1: List of reference material to be used

1. SOP for sensory characterization of fufu, and retting ability developed within the RTBfoods project <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00595>.
2. SOP for Firmness of Cassava genotypes during Retting using the hand-held Penetrometer <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00734>
3. SOP for textural characterization of Fufu. Umudike, Nigeria <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00612>
4. SOP for fufu textural analysis¹⁶ and sensory texture profile analysis (STPA) <https://doi.org/10.18167/DVN1/RFZMLC>
5. SOP for sensory characterization of Fufu. Umudike, Nigeria <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00595>
6. Monitoring panel performance and cleaning data from descriptive sensory panels for statistical analysis <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00582>
7. Training a panel in sensory analysis and implementing descriptive tests. How to process data <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00573>

Appendix 2: RHUL team feedback:

Experimental design and planning is outstanding and compliant with metabolomics guidelines defined in the project. Very much appreciated the efforts in adapting methodology for metabolomics analysis and looking forward to analysing the sample set.

Please see below comments/feedback:

Q1: do we know the parents of the bi-parental populations used in this study, i.e, NR20C3 and NR23S? Are the parents included in the field trials too? Same for the Genetic Gains collection. This information will be handy later for publications.

Q2: in Table 1, the column marked with an “X” mean that phenotypic data has been performed previously and is available? If so, could you please provide the phenotypic records and corresponding scoring classification? Or indicate how/where to access this information.

Q3: could you please provide the list of genotypes included in Figure 1? Presumably these genotypes are from NR20C3 population but annotations of figure 1 and table 1 are different. Also indicate where/how to access the phenotypic data used for the retting classification.

Q4: If I understand correctly Figure 2, each plant/stand will be processed individually, thus producing 6 biological independent replicates per genotype, is this correct? It is not clear to me if the 3 roots per plant from all 6 plants (from 8.1 to 8.6) will be pooled in a single vat at retting stage (step 3, page 7), and after processing and cooking (step 3 and 4), 6 aliquots of the pooled plants will be taken and freeze-dried.

Q5: In Figure 2, please freeze-dry the sample as intact slices/cubes and send to RHUL as freeze-dried pieces. Homogenisation of tissue will be performed here at RHUL.

Q6: based on the tentative chronogram (table 2), estimated shipment of sample to RHUL will be January-February 2026?

Q7: any publications/references available?